

CACAO

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CyVerse is funded by the Arizona Board of Regents and the US National Science Foundation under award Nos. DBI-0735191, DBI-1265383, and DBI-1743442

Cloud Automation Continuous Analysis Orchestration

cacao

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What is CACAO?

CACAO is a **multi-cloud** software platform that enables **researchers, educators, research software professionals** (RSPs) to create, use, and share their **data-driven workflows, infrastructure, and software stacks**, while allowing them to minimize costs by leveraging **cloud frameworks**.

ANSIBLE

elastic

HashiCorp
Vault

redis

fluentd

kubernetes

kibana

Challenges when Using Cloud

Doing **collaborative**, data-driven team science in the cloud is challenging. Effective science in the cloud requires **deep technical understanding** of each cloud provider's capabilities and **cost**.

*"I don't want to know where it's computing.
I don't want to know where my data is... When
I'm done, publish that function so that other
people can do it."*

-- Nate Miller, UW Madison, Plant Biologist

HashiCorp
Terraform

ANSIBLE

kubernetes

CLI

Web

 = Microservice

Templates: Cloud frameworks, DSLs, IaC

Jetstream2

Other Cloud Service Providers

Self-Provision Applications To Any Cloud

- Researcher
- Educator
- RSE

CSP

Edge Clouds

What about Templates?

Name
..
.cacao
ansible
hosts.yml.tmpl
inputs.tf
main.tf
output-ansible-inventory.tf
outputs.tf

The core technology revolves around cloud frameworks, IaC, DSLs

Require these to be currently stored in

We don't require any other changes to the templates, other than a couple of metadata files located in **.cacao** folder

What about Templates?

```
{
  "schema_url": "https://gitlab.com/cyverse/cacao-common/-/raw/master/template/m
  "schema_version": "3",
  "name": "single image openstack instances",
  "author": "Edwin Skidmore",
  "author_email": "edwin@cyverse.org",
  "description": "simple launch of one or more vms",
  "template_type": "openstack_terraform",
  "purpose": "openstack_compute",
  "cacao_pre_tasks": [],
  "cacao_post_tasks": [
    {
      "type": "ansible",
      "location": "cacao_atmosphere_legacy"
    }
  ],
  "parameters": [
    {
      "name": "username",
      "type": "cacao_username",
      "default": "username",
      "description": "CACAO username"
    },
    {
      "name": "region",
      "type": "cacao_provider_region",
      "default": "IU",
      "description": "Openstack region"
    },
    {
      "name": "instance_name",
      "type": "cacao_instance_name"
    }
  ]
}
```

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.cacao/metadata.json

What about Templates?

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.cacao/metadata.json
.cacao/ui.json (optional)

The screenshot shows a web interface for creating a new deployment. The title bar reads "New Deployment: openstack-single-image" and "JETSTREAM 2 / TRA220028". The form is divided into two steps: "1 Parameters" and "2 Review & Deploy".

Under "1 Parameters", there are several input fields:

- "Choose Region" dropdown menu with "IU" selected.
- "Instance name *" text input field with "my-instance-name" entered.
- A light blue notification box with an information icon and the text "Windows server images are not yet supported."
- "Boot image name" dropdown menu with "Featured-Ubuntu22" selected.
- "# of Instances *" dropdown menu with "1" selected.
- "Size" dropdown menu with "g3.small GPU" selected.
- An "Advanced" section with an upward arrow and a toggle switch for "Configure boot disk" which is currently turned off.

At the bottom of the form, there are two buttons: "START OVER" and "NEXT".

Below the form, a snippet of JSON code is visible:

```
{
  "type": "row",
  "items": [
    {
```


CyVerse-curated CACAO Templates

<u>Template</u>	<u>Purpose</u>
single-image	Deploy one or more instances
single-image-k3s	Deploy a k3s cluster with multiple nodes
vms4workshop	Deploy a set of instances with instructor and separate student instances, with a desktop and ssh access
single-image-docker	Deploy one or more instances configured as a docker stacks
cacao-tf-jupyterhub	Deploy a Zero to JupyterHub with multiple nodes configurable GPUs, Shared Storage, and other configurable options
cacao-tf-llama2	Deploy quantized version of OS LLMs on local CPU inference derived by K. Leung

Projects Using CACAO

<u>Project</u>	<u>Type</u>	<u>Description</u>
JetStream2	Infra	(OpenStack) Cloud for science and engineering
HydroGEN	MLOps	ML-based simulation platform to simulate hydrological scenarios with the goal of elastic scaling to AWS
COALESCE (Context Aware Learning for Sustainable Cyber-agriculture systems)	Edge	Innovation by combining digital agricultural tools (e.g., robotics) and physical tools (e.g., sensors and drones;) ML compute to the edge (farm sites)
AIIRA (AI Institute for Resilient Agriculture)	MLOps	Deploying AI-driven predictive digital twins for modeling plants to increase resiliency of the nation's agricultural systems; MLOps in the cloud
BisQue	IaaS	Deploy their imaging platform to the cloud
DADI (Diffusion Approximation for Demographic Inference, NIH)	SaaS	Uses CACAO to deploy DADI software to OpenStack and in the future AWS
ESILL	SaaS	Deploy Jupyter environments to support collaboration and innovation
Open Forestry Observatory	IaaS	Deploy components of the Open Forestry platform
University of Arizona Space4 Institute	Edge	Distributed multi-tier cloud/edge cloud executing event-driven Kubernetes workflows with auto-deployments of new methods

Workshops powered by CACAO

- 11 Workshops
- 4 Countries
- > 450 Students

<u>Year</u>	<u>Workshop/Location</u>
2022	TrAC Training, Iowa State University, USA
	CyVerse Container Camp, University of Arizona, USA
	AZ Geospatial Information Council, Prescott, AZ, USA
	CompBio Asia, Bangkok, Thailand
	Transposon Symposium, Uppsala, Sweden
	Sensing Earth II, Haskell Indian Nations University, Kansas, US
2023	Forest Resilience WG, CU Boulder, USA
	ESII Science Summit, CU Boulder, USA
	CompBio Asia 2023, Singapore
	CyVerse Cloud Native Camp, University of Arizona, USA
	US Forestry Service, USA

Home

Deployments

Credentials

Templates

Help

Cloud Automation & Continuous Analysis Orchestration

Hi there, this is a Beta release.

I GOT SOME FEEDBACK

Allocations

Jetstream2 Affiliated Development Projects TRA220028

You have 16 days remaining of current allocation.

CyVerse Discovery Environment Machine Learning development environments enabled by Jetstream CIS220026

Today
You have 210 days remaining of current allocation.

Future Work

- Better feedback when the cloud fails and other faults outside of cloud framework fails
- Ability to chain deployments e.g. deploy a Kubernetes and then deploy a workflow that operates in Kubernetes
- Integrating other domain specific frameworks like ML-specific frameworks (e.g. Ray ML, Kubeflow), Nextflow (<https://www.nextflow.io/>) or SkyPilot (<https://sky.cs.berkeley.edu/>)
- Adding more templates from the community

Future Collaborations

Got a project or collaboration that has challenges in using the cloud?

CyVerse welcomes opportunities to discuss how to leverage CACAO to access and use cloud frameworks to solve those problems.

Thank you

Repo: gitlab.com/cyverse/cacao (Of course, we're Open Source)

URL: cacao.jetstream-cloud.org (via ACCESS)

The Team (reverse alpha order)

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